

Participant P1

Formative Evaluation Round - I Code Quality Documents

Thank you for participating in our formative evaluation of the Code Quality Documents. Our documents are interactive reports that combine automatically generated text and visualizations to express the code quality of a given project.

This study consists of three parts and would take approximately 45 minutes. Our system is available as a Web application.

Part-I: [15 min] Exploration Task

*You are presented with the code quality document of **xerces** project. Using our system, summarize (in your own words) what are the main quality aspects that are discussed.*

Cohesion, bugs, inheritance, spaghetti, blob, coupling. Some good, some bad. I wouldn't know but the text explains it. Nice!

Part-II: [25 min] Feedback

No.	Question	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1.	The presented information is useful?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	The quality of the presented content is very good?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
3.	The document is self-contained and self-explanatory?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
4.	The generated text is very interesting to read?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	The generated text and visualizations are well connected?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6.	The visualizations (parallel coordinates and scatter plot) are most suitable for the intended purpose?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Please justify your ratings and answer the following questions. Feel free to write as much as you like.

1. What information do you find most useful?

Focus on bad stuff. Call attention of dev to problems. Links between document and code.

2. What information do you not find useful?

SLs in 3 and PCP. There is no link to the code, no labels of classes. No legend to explain the colors. No explanation for prefiltered axes and no way of going from the lines (in PCP) to the code.

3. What other information would you like to see in the document?

Links to specific locations in code. Otherwise I know there is a problem in a class but I don't know where.

How are bugs defined? Compilation errors? Because I couldn't imagine how functional bugs are identified automatically.

4. Do you think that the document is self-contained and self-explanatory?

Yes, mostly. Not self-explanatory when it comes to the dimension in the scatter plot.

5. What are the most important interactions?

Links between report and code.

6. What other interactions would like to see?

Ranking of classes that need most work.

7. Do the word-sized graphics better connect text and visualizations?

Yes. But for me they seem more like a different view on the data. Like "109 classes (<percentage>) have bla blub". It could also be presented as text. But it fits nicely because it has extra information without being too intrusive.

Would like to see different color scales in these percentages. The text says the value is good or bad, but the color does not reflect that. It always looks like everything is fine (green bars).

8. Do you find visualizations (Parallel coordinates and scatterplot) appropriate for the intended purpose?

Could be. But not right now. Parallel coordinates do not show what class is being visualized and do not provide link to code. Scatter plot uses too many abbreviations that I don't know.

9. Are the text and corresponding visualizations interactively linked in an intuitive way?

I did not find a link from the visualization to the text. But the other way round works nicely.

Part-III: [5 min] Interview

1. How do you compare our system with a conventional Visual Analytic system or software quality software?

Your system is good because it summarizes the content very well. The analysis behind text looks very robust.

2. Would you prefer a pure visualization based approach with annotated textual explanations? Why?

It depends. In your system, the data is given context, which is nice. If I focus on vis part then I would like it to explain things from annotations.

Participant P2

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Part-I: [15 min] Exploration Task

*You are presented with the code quality document of **xerces** project. Using our system, summarize (in your own words) what are the main quality aspects that are discussed.*

The tool allows to analyze bad smells such as blobs, functional decomposition, spaghetti code, and lazy class; and bugs. It also helps to analyze some general quality attributes such as coupling, complexity, cohesion, and inheritance.

Part-II: [25 min] Feedback

No.	Question	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1.	The presented information is useful?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2.	The quality of the presented content is very good?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	The document is self-contained and self-explanatory?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	The generated text is very interesting to read?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	The generated text and visualizations are well connected?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6.	The visualizations (parallel coordinates and scatter plot) are	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

	most suitable for the intended purpose?					
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Please justify your ratings and answer the following questions. Feel free to write as much as you like.

1. What information do you find most useful?

The list of the quality issues, and the details showing the involved classes. Also the companion scatter plot seems useful.

2. What information do you not find useful?

The list of the metrics in the scatter plot is not explained, and thus the scatter plot is not very useful in practice. The bar charts are not well connected with the general quality attributes. The vertical labels are hard to read, and the colored segments of the bars are not explained. The sparklines in the text are somehow distracting, and maybe too colorful. It is hard to read the text with the sparklines in between.

3. What other information would you like to see in the document?

A visualization that shows an overview of the quality, in which I can dig into details of specific components without losing the overview (like a map). Instead of composing the multiple aspects of code quality into a paragraph I would prefer to list them.

4. Do you think that the document is self-contained and self-explanatory?

The goal is very broad, so it is hard for the document to be self-contained. However, I can imagine several uses for the document as it is. Some parts of the document such as the bar charts and parallel coordinates have a not clear purpose.

5. What are the most important interactions?

To get details of the classes involved in the quality issues, and interactions with the visualizations to analyze particularities in the code.

6. What other interactions would you like to see?

Maybe some coordinates views that highlight how a particular class is involved in the various aspects of quality. Maybe at different granularity levels (e.g., package).

7. Do the word-sized graphics better connect text and visualizations?

They provide an advantage in terms of giving a context to a number. However, I found them too distractive, and made the reading harder.

8. Do you find visualizations (Parallel coordinates and scatterplot) appropriate for the intended purpose?

Maybe they would be useful to assess some hypotheses, but for exploratory analysis it is not so clear how to use them. They lack of a legend, and an explanation of how they are expected to be used. They also contain some interactions that are hard to discover.

9. Are the text and corresponding visualizations interactively linked in an intuitive way?

Somehow.

Part-III: [5 min] Interview

1. How do you compare our system with a conventional Visual Analytic system or software quality software?

It is nice to see discussion on some quality aspects of code. The tool analyzes the data well; interactions and details of code are useful. It gives a nice overview at the start and then different ways to go to the details.

2. Would you prefer a pure visualization based approach with annotated textual explanations? Why?

I would prefer a pure visualization approach but your tool is more balanced in terms of textual details and visualizations. Non-vis people would find the system more useful. It is a better trade-off.

Participant P3

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Part-I: [15 min] Exploration Task

*You are presented with the code quality document of **xerces** project. Using our system, summarize (in your own words) what are the main quality aspects that are discussed.*

The system provides an overview of the xerces project's software quality metrics. It gives an overview in 3 main categories: bad smells, bugs, and general quality attributes.

The main part of the application consists of textual information, enriched with simple/small charts (bar charts, filled bars, etc.).

Much of the information is color coded. Main colors are red, yellow, blue, and green. In Section 3 ("General Quality Attributes") it looks like red/green are used to convey a bad/good message.

In the initial loading stage of the application the left hand side shows an interactive PCP.

The right side of the application is context-sensitive and shows information based on what the user clicked. This includes interactive scatter plots, directory listings and a source code view.

Part-II: [25 min] Feedback

No.	Question	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
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2.	The quality of the presented content is very good?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	The document is self-contained and self-explanatory?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	The generated text is very interesting to read?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	The generated text and visualizations are well connected?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
6.	The visualizations (parallel coordinates and scatter plot) are most suitable for the intended purpose?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Please justify your ratings and answer the following questions. Feel free to write as much as you like.

1. What information do you find most useful?

Detection of Bad Smells

2. What information do you not find useful?

Introductory text before Bad Smells

3. What other information would you like to see in the document?

Information from the Version Control system (number of commits, date of last commit, number of commit authors, etc.)

4. Do you think that the document is self-contained and self-explanatory?

Self-contained: yes, self-explanatory: no. I have a hard time trying to figure out the meanings of the acronyms in PCP and scatter plot (loc, npm, lcom3, etc.)

5. What are the most important interactions?

Details on demand: selecting one thing in the left panel and getting more details on this in the right panel.

6. What other interactions would you like to see?

Maybe focusing on one of the sections (bad smells, bugs, general quality attributes) by collapsing the other two.

7. Do the word-sized graphics better connect text and visualizations?

Yes

8. Do you find visualizations (Parallel coordinates and scatterplot) appropriate for the intended purpose?

The PCP is quite hard to read. The placing (initially ~60% are off-screen, scrolling is needed) is bad, and the number of metrics and scales and scale labels is a bit intimidating. Combined with the fact, that I don't understand the displayed metrics, this plot is hard for me to find useful.

9. Are the text and corresponding visualizations interactively linked in an intuitive way?

Yes

Part-III: [5 min] Interview

1. How do you compare our system with a conventional Visual Analytic system or software quality software?

Some sections of the text are very machine-generated and really boring to read. The other reads well and adds value. But use of natural language is a good idea here because it is more explanatory compared to visualizations.

2. Would you prefer a pure visualization based approach with annotated textual explanations? Why?

It really depends on the application. But for this case, I would prefer the combination of text and visualization and not the visualization as a core with textual explanations.

Participant P4

Formative Evaluation Round - I Code Quality Documents

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This study consists of three parts and would take approximately 45 minutes. Our system is available as a Web application.

Part-I: [15 min] Exploration Task

*You are presented with the code quality document of **xerces** project. Using our system, summarize (in your own words) what are the main quality aspects that are discussed.*

I think the main quality aspects are: coupling, complexity, cohesion, and inheritance. I don't understand what is the meaning of bad smells, but they are also discussed in the document.

From the document it can be inferred that in xerces, cohesion is the major problem.

Part-II: [25 min] Feedback

No.	Question	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
1.	The presented information is useful?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2.	The quality of the presented content is very good?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3.	The document is self-contained and self-explanatory?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4.	The generated text is very interesting to read?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5.	The generated text and visualizations are well connected?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

6.	The visualizations (parallel coordinates and scatter plot) are most suitable for the intended purpose?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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Please justify your ratings and answer the following questions. Feel free to write as much as you like.

1. What information do you find most useful?

Summary of how the code performs in terms of four general quality attributes was most useful along with the percentage bars for classes. Visualizations along with the text were helpful to understand what they were showing.

2. What information do you not find useful?

- a. I was confused with the separation of bad smells and bugs with general quality attributes. Are the former two not indicators of code quality?
- b. I was not able to understand what a bad smell is in terms of code quality.
- c. "xerces has 14 bad smells" -> and then it shows a bar chart with 4 bars. I did not understand what this bar chart represents. If it shows frequency of 14 bad smells then why only 4 were shown?
- d. I found the color of horizontal percentage bars confusing. The green color was same in few percentage bars and in the starting space of sub-sections of section 3 (except sec 3.3). I think they are indicating whether the quality measure was good or bad but usage of same green color confused me.
- e. "The sparklines below are created using values of the metrics respective to these four quality attributes. To add meaningful interpretation, the stacked-bar charts are structured with respect to packages." -> I do not see sparklines and stacked bar charts.
- f. I absolutely got lost with the grouping of code quality attributes. A blob is a bad thing to have in the code and is discussed under Bad smells along with other quality measures like spaghetti code. Then general quality attributes are discussed such as complexity, cohesion etc, but are different from bad smells? I didn't get it.

3. What other information would you like to see in the document?

I would like to see the definitions of the quality measures, as I do not know them.

4. Do you think that the document is self-contained and self-explanatory?

Yes, but there are few areas to improve.:

1. Definitions of quality measures.
2. Color legends

3. Legend for explaining acronyms of code quality measures. Eg. "loc -> Lines of code".

5. What are the most important interactions?

1. Clickable links.
2. Plus signs for more details

6. What other interactions would you like to see?

Click or tap here to enter text.

7. Do the word-sized graphics better connect text and visualizations?

Yes, absolutely.

8. Do you find visualizations (Parallel coordinates and scatterplot) appropriate for the intended purpose?

I find them appropriate but parallel co-ordinates need some improvement to understand it better. I got confused in understanding that each line in the plot shows information for a single class.

9. Are the text and corresponding visualizations interactively linked in an intuitive way?

Yes

Part-III: [5 min] Interview

1. How do you compare our system with a conventional Visual Analytic system or software quality software?

It is indeed a Visual analytic system but it offers less exploration compared to conventional VA systems. Of course, text is more explicit and conveys things more vividly.

2. Would you prefer a pure visualization based approach with annotated textual explanations? Why?

It depends on the application or target user group. With the current representation it is more going towards the summarization of the code quality and could be good for getting an overview but do not offer much exploration options to do in-depth analysis. For instance, users can see where the bug is (just the source code of the class) but it is not really possible to see if the same bug appears in multiple classes or are there repetitive patterns of bugs? However, correlations (Scatter plot) might already be very helpful for the developers. The tool won't be very useful for the developers in fact in its current state.

